

The Blue Economy and Knowledge Co-Production in Seychelles

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The Blue Economy is the formal term used when describing ocean-based sustainable development. Sustainability is at the heart of the Blue Economy. Globally, and particularly for coastal and ocean nations, there is a focus on developing coastal and ocean spaces to advance opportunity, equality and prosperity. Nations have relied on, and continue to rely on the ocean for transport, food and climate regulation, to name a few. The difference now, however, is that there is an intense focus on how best to develop this space in a more sustainable way, ensuring prosperity for humankind, but also a healthy ocean.

The term ‘Blue Economy’ (as linked to sustainable development discourse in the international political arena) emerged out of the 2012 United Nations Rio+20 Conference on Sustainable Development. Small Island Developing States in particular face many social, economic and environmental challenges when it comes to successfully advancing sustainable development. Instead of focusing on the Green Economy during Rio+20, coastal and island nations recognized the important role that their ‘blue’ space could play in advancing sustainable development. During the Third Conference of Small Island Developing States in Samoa in 2014, island nations voiced their commonalities and the importance of developing their ocean space to enhance their own livelihoods and wellbeing, as well as that of the global community. Seychelles has embraced the opportunity provided by the international recognition of the Blue Economy, and many locally-facilitated initiatives have evolved from this. One particular initiative is hosted by the University of Seychelles (UniSey).

UniSey was established in 2009 and has developed a range of internationally accepted qualifications, including an undergraduate programme in Environmental Science. In March 2015, UniSey established its first research institute – the Blue Economy Research Institute (BERI). BERI currently operates within UniSey’s framework of operations. In honour of the previous president of Seychelles, who is an ambassador for the Blue Economy, *James Michel* was later added to the title and is included (in italics) in all formal communications and materials. BERI was developed to support research in the area of environmental science, specifically relating to the Blue Economy, and supporting integrated and adaptive ocean management. A postgraduate programme in Marine Science and Sustainability has been added to UniSey’s portfolio since the inception of BERI.

BERI's strategy focuses on three core pillars:

1. Creating an enabling environment for locally-driven academic research

The aim of this pillar is to attract human and financial capital and the physical resources needed to facilitate research management, development and generation. The Blue Economy requires the consolidation of knowledge across social, ecological, economic and governance disciplines. Ideally, BERI aims to host expert groups in each of these thematic areas, in a space that facilitates collaboration and knowledge sharing between disciplines. This is being done transitionally, to facilitate the expansion of each discipline as experience and finances evolve at UniSey, by using existing frameworks and resources while encouraging development beyond the status quo. One of the challenges related to being such a young institute in a country with a limited history of locally-driven academic research generation is the lack of evidence and reputation needed to attract funding and partnerships. Thus, another core aspect of this pillar is to establish local and international relationships. This builds trust to support research uptake and develop local and international collaboration to strengthen research impact and quality, while simultaneously assisting in human capacity building and development to help mainstream the Blue Economy throughout Seychelles.

2. Strengthening transdisciplinary academic research synergy and outputs

This pillar focuses on supporting quality-controlled and 'home-grown' research generation, with an emphasis on baseline data generation (and retention) as a short-term priority. This aims to assist decision makers and practitioners who are working in the 'blue' space and to create a culture of research uptake and collaboration. Furthermore, it allows UniSey to build on its strengths to ensure that this new area of research management and administration evolves alongside BERI. Examples include work related to baseline ecosystem mapping and monitoring (coral, seagrass, macroalgae, etc.) and ocean acidification. There is also a natural research progression into areas related to ecosystem valuation and climate change adaptation and resilience (which is linked to ocean health and human wellbeing), and other Blue Economy-related areas as capacity, resources and infrastructure have increased, and continue to increase (i.e., long term priorities). See the figure below for a more detailed depiction of BERI's technical focus areas.

UniSey is located in Anse Royale, within a natural laboratory, where a ridge to reef (and beyond) approach can be applied. While BERI aims to support local research development and uptake across various areas in Seychelles, where feasible, consistent efforts are being made to build and retain local long-term data in the Anse Royale area. This is being done to

develop a research site that shows trends over time, illustrate ecosystem connectivity, and to facilitate systems thinking. Various other research is also taking place across other islands in collaboration with local partners. Other projects are being developed to expand on core themes of the Blue Economy, attracting international collaboration, knowledge exchange and local and international student engagement in these areas, especially aquaculture. The young and small nature of UniSey allows for close collaboration between departments. This enables research project collaboration with colleagues from the law, business, and computing and information systems departments, supporting the interdisciplinary nature of Blue Economy research. Research collaboration is also expanding into areas outside of academia, working with multiple stakeholders from the private sector and the general community to enable transdisciplinary research that supports knowledge co-production in support of transformative change. BERI attracts experienced researchers and has an extensive local, regional and international network. This allows BERI to be well placed in local committees and initiatives in order to support and advise on multiple national projects and initiatives, further empowering decision making, adaptive management and science-policy integration. The dynamic, complex and diverse nature of research-related activities linked to the Blue Economy require hands-on coordination, evaluation, and relationship management to ensure that the research being undertaken is creating a meaningful impact and evolving over time.

SUMMARY OF BERI'S TECHNICAL FOCUS AREAS

ECOSYSTEM CHANGE

Monitoring, Protection, Restoration:
including Ocean Acidification, Coral
Reef Resilience and Function
and Blue Carbon

Short-term
development priority

Core capacity, with local and
international collaboration

WATER QUALITY

Biological, Physical, and Chemical
(Ridge to Reef)

Medium-term
development priority

Core capacity, with local and
international collaboration

BLUE ECONOMY SECTORS

Fisheries and Aquaculture, Coastal and
Marine Tourism, Coastal Development,
Renewable Energy, Marine Biotechnology,
Seabed Mining

Long-term development priority, but
with ad hoc support where needed
and feasible

Cross-faculty/Research Institute engagement,
strong local and international collaboration

OCEAN GOVERNANCE, INTEGRATED OCEAN MANAGEMENT AND BLUE ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Including Climate Change Adaptation and Resilience, Natural Resource Economics and Ecosystem Valuation
and Waste Management and Assimilation

Long-term development priority, some core capacity as well as additional ad hoc support where needed and feasible
Cross-faculty/Research Institute engagement, strong local and international collaboration

3. Empowering Blue Guardians to safeguard the ocean and support research

Although academia benefits from cross-fertilization when academic minds come together (local and international), growing and sustaining long-term local capacity and data is vital if the Blue Economy is to provide maximum benefit to the local community. This pillar aims to foster knowledge generation and co-production. Various education and awareness activities are facilitated in collaboration with the University Centre for Environmental Education (UniSey's environmental community outreach center). This inspires ocean awareness at an early age to mentor and groom interested young students in order to build a future workforce and support ocean advocacy. National and international internships enable research data to expand and students to learn from each other. Local and international symposiums and other events are facilitated and open to local students and the wider public. Laboratory equipment is maintained, updated and made available to national partners. Students are exposed to useful instruments and technology housed and maintained within the ever-evolving laboratories. A coral library has been developed in collaboration with local partners and continues to grow. Massive Open Online Courses on the Blue Economy have allowed people from all walks of life (locally and internationally) to learn more. Researchers support UniSey degree programs (across faculties) and co-publish with local research officers and students in order to help build core skills and knowledge that are transferable across disciplines. BERI is also working with local partners to ensure Seychelles becomes an Ocean Knowledge-Action Network (KAN) hub which aims to support the UN Decade for Ocean Sciences and to be a pillar in the acceleration of transformative action in Seychelles and the Western Indian Ocean.

Transformational change is vital if Seychelles is to address the challenges it is facing, and will continue to face, as exploration and expansion takes place in this 'blue' space. Research plays a key role in supporting transformation and empowering decision makers, entrepreneurs, business owners, practitioners and users of the coastal and ocean space. It also allows the wider community to take an interest in decisions and practices that may impact the quality of this 'blue' space. Although UniSey is a small university facing many of the challenges common to Small Island Developing States, it plays a key role in enabling transformational change. One of the benefits of being a young university is the opportunity for innovation. UniSey continues to facilitate access to resources, education and networks that support local and collaborative knowledge development, co-production and capacity development.

Establishing and sustaining a research institute in such a dynamic environment with such a diverse range of disciplines and stakeholders requires adaptive management and the development of local and international relationships and networks. With the right focus and strong research management at various levels to support successful research development and delivery, BERI has the potential to grow its active research and knowledge network to support an informed, fair and sustainable Blue Economy.

Kelly Hoareau is the former and founding Director of the James Michel Blue Economy Research Institute at the University of Seychelles. Within Seychelles, she is actively developing academic resources, networks and knowledge to support the Seychelles Blue Economy agenda. Internationally, she contributes to research, education and awareness to advance ocean-based sustainable development, and is undertaking a PhD with Australia's Blue Economy Cooperative Research Centre through the University of Tasmania. Kelly has first-hand experience of working in Africa and with various small island developing states and coastal nations, across marine and terrestrial ecosystems. Coupled with her engagement with academic, government, private and non-governmental entities, this has led to her interest in transdisciplinary research and knowledge co-production that enables innovative ocean-based sustainable development. Follow her on Twitter: @KellyHoareau

For foundational information about the Blue Economy refer to this link.

https://www.oceanprosperityroadmap.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/2.-State-of-the-Blue-Economy_briefing-paper_WOS2015.pdf

Below are images of a selection of activities which have taken place over the last few years

***BERI representing and supporting Blue Economy-related academic research as part of the national delegation at various conferences and events
(Photographs © K. Hoareau)***

*Launch of Coral Library at UniSey
(Main partners: Government of Seychelles / UNDP / Global Environment Facility Outer Islands Project)
(Photographs © K. Hoareau)*

*BERI researchers joining the collaboration on the Nekton First Descent expedition in Seychelles
(Photographs © J. Harlay)*

*BERI researchers supporting local coral monitoring at various locations/islands
(Main partners: Green Islands Foundation, Fregate Island Private)
(Photographs © H. Anlauf/S. Laing)*

Sargassum rope culture as part of Integrated Multitrophic Aquaculture (IMTA) experiments in support of Seychelles' Aquaculture Development Plan
(Photographs © N. Gordon)

*BSc. Environmental Sciences students on field excursion for Natural Resource Economics course – assisting SFA fisheries observers at local artisanal fish markets
(Photographs © N. Gordon)*

BSc. Environmental Sciences undergraduate students and local interns training on water quality and invertebrate sample processing

(Photographs © N. Gordon)

Ms Mariette Dine, UniSey graduate and Seychelles Conservation and Climate Adaptation Trust grant holder investigating the potential of generating bioplastics from local seaweed species in UniSey's laboratories

(Photographs © M. Dine)

*BERI researchers undertaking seagrass mapping and training with local and international partners (main partners: Pew Charitable Trust, University of Oxford and Seychelles Conservation and Climate Adaptation Trust)
(Photographs © J. Harlay)*